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Research Article

**INVESTIGATION OF DIET PATTERN, ANTHROPOMETRY,
AND HANDGRIP STRENGTH OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE
PATIENT UNDERGOING HEMODIALYSIS IN TERTIARY
CARE HOSPITAL****P. Suriya**Assistant Professor, Dept of Renal dialysis technology, Grace college of Allied Health Science,
Padanthalumoodu, The Tamil Nadu DR.MGR Medical University, Chennai-600032.**Abstract:**

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is known as kidney damage that last longer than three months, as determined by structural or functional abnormalities of the kidney, with or without a reduction in Glomerular Filtration Rate, according to KDIGO. OR Regardless of the cause, chronic kidney disease is characterized as kidney damage or a GFR of under 60ml/min/1.73m for three months or longer. ⁽¹⁾ Dietary pattern analysis has emerged as a realistic tool for analyzing both qualitative & quantitative aspects of a person's overall diet, taking into account the simultaneous effects of various food products and dietetic elements, and also their interactions. Nutritional methods have a strong role to play to stop or delay the growth and consequences of CKD. A healthy, well-balanced diet is essential for good health and nutrition. It provides protection against a wide range of chronic non-communicable diseases, including heart disease, diabetes, and cancer. Consuming less salt, sweets, saturated fats, and trans fats from industrial sources, as well as eating a variety of foods, is essential for a balanced diet. ⁽⁸⁾ Several approaches are used to assess hemodialysis patients' nutritional status. We studied patient's regular dietary pattern and their nutritional status by using the handgrip and anthropometry measurements.

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INTRODUCTION:

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is known as kidney damage that last longer than three months, as determined by structural or functional abnormalities of the kidney, with or without a reduction in Glomerular Filtration Rate, according to KDIGO. OR Regardless of the cause, chronic kidney disease is characterized as kidney damage or a GFR of under 60ml/min/1.73m for three months or longer. ⁽¹⁾ Dietary pattern analysis has emerged as a realistic tool for analyzing both qualitative & quantitative aspects of a person's overall diet, taking into account the simultaneous effects of various food products and dietetic elements, and also their interactions. Nutritional methods have a strong role to play to stop or delay the growth and consequences of CKD.

The risk of cardiovascular mortality is 30 times greater in end-stage renal disease (ESRD) compare to the general population. ⁽²⁾ The major reason for death among HD patients is cardiovascular disease (CVD) and is linked with a higher incidence of the typical risk factors, including hypertension, diabetes mellitus (DM), dyslipidemia, obesity, and advanced age. Often factors include edema, hyperphosphatemia, anemia, left ventricular hypertrophy, inflammation, oxidative stress, and endothelial dysfunction. ⁽³⁾

Micronutrient consumption is suggested by clinical guidelines and it is advised to avoid hyperphosphatemia, hyperkalemia, hypertension, and water retention. Food restriction can lead to malnutrition, although the specifics of dietary patterns that may increase hemodialysis patient outcomes are uncertain. ⁽⁹⁾ Persons with ESKD who are on hemodialysis should change their eating habits. To minimize increased blood electrolyte levels and the accompanying cardiovascular problems, clinical practice guidelines prescribe limiting phosphate, potassium, and sodium consumption ⁽¹⁰⁾. Handgrip strength (HGS) is simple test in medicine and is used to define many important phenotypes such as malnutrition and frailty. These ideas have also been explored in the dialysis patient group, with significant incidence and a significant link to mortality. A dynamometer is used to test HGS in the traditional way. In the elderly population, the procedure is simple, quick, cheap, and standardized. ⁽⁴⁾ Handgrip strength (HGS) has emerged as a viable approach to determining nutritional quality in clinical practice. Nonetheless, because it is a test for assessing voluntary muscular strength, it is highly connected with body mass, provided it is feasible to identify individuals who had a severe decline in dietary patterns prior to any change. ⁽¹¹⁾

Handgrip strength is a non-invasive, quick, objective, and economical method, which measures the maximal voluntary strength of the hand/arm, has been regarded as a valuable tool in measuring muscle function (MF). In surgical patients and in the elderly, this method has been linked to death and complications. ⁽¹²⁾ Anthropometry is collection of quantitative measures of muscle, bone, and adipose tissue that are used to assess the composition of the human body. Height, weight, body mass index (BMI), body circumferences like waist, hip, and limbs, and skinfold thickness of biceps and triceps are the basic components of anthropometry. ⁽⁵⁾ In individuals with chronic renal disease, good dietary status is a well-known indicator of health (CKD). Protein energy malnutrition (PEM) occurs as CKD progresses and is linked to poor outcomes. Although most overt uremia symptoms fade or vanish after starting Hemodialysis (HD), the dialysis method may induce wasting through a variety of mechanisms. Acidosis and enhanced catabolism are both essential factors in the cause of protein energy malnutrition (PEM) in HD patients. Nutritional status and the dialysis adequacy index are two important factors that influence mortality and morbidity in MHD patients. ⁽⁶⁾ Food frequency questionnaires (FFQ) are usually good for ranking participants in a specific group based on their nutrient consumption over a longer time period, as opposed to dietary recalls and food records, which are used to measure dietary consumption at the individual level and over shorter time period: With the growing cases of CKD patients, particularly those receiving Dialysis in outside dialysis clinics, frequent nutritional assessments, and comparisons of dialysis patients, nutritional intake may assist in improving clinical outcomes linked to nutrition. ⁽⁷⁾

A healthy, well-balanced diet is essential for good health and nutrition. It provides protection against a wide range of chronic non-communicable diseases, including heart disease, diabetes, and cancer. Consuming less salt, sweets, saturated fats, and trans fats from industrial sources, as well as eating a variety of foods, is essential for a balanced diet. ⁽⁸⁾ Several approaches are used to assess hemodialysis patients' nutritional status. We studied patient's regular dietary pattern and their nutritional status by using the handgrip and anthropometry measurements.

Review of literature

Literature for this study was identified by searching Pub Med, Single window search, Wiley, and Scopus. The search terms were as follows "dietary pattern in hemodialysis patients, anthropometry, handgrip strength, chronic kidney disease".

Fernanda Santin et.al did a cross-sectional study namely "Dietary pattern of patients with chronic kidney disease: the influence of treatment modality" in Brazil. The goal of this study was to relate dietary patterns of CKD patients with their modality of treatment. In 839 individuals with a self-reported diagnosis of non-dialysis (n = 480), dialysis (n = 48) or renal transplantation (n = 17) therapy (n = 294) weekly review of 14 dietary intake markers was examined. Results show that two food trends were identified: the pattern "Unhealthy" and "Healthy". Non-dialysis and dialysis therapy were inversely correlated with the Unhealthy trend. At the same time, renal transplant treatment was favorably associated with the Stable healthy pattern, and author the concluded that in Brazilian CKD patients, two dietary patterns were discovered, that is the healthy pattern and unhealthy pattern, and these patterns were related to the chronic kidney disease treatment modality. Limitation are Food intake indicators, like most ways of measuring food intake, are minimal instruments and do not collect information on all foods eaten. Furthermore, since certain populations have limited sampling sizes and therefore poor statistical capacity, it is possible that substantial variations would be missed. ⁽²⁾

The study named "Handgrip strength measurement in hemodialysis patients before and after the session" by author Pierre Delanaye et.al in Belgium assessed adult hemodialysis patients on the same day before and immediately after disconnection. Each test was repeated three times with a 5-second measurement interval with the higher value taken for analysis. The result came as, after dialysis, there was a substantial decrease in HGS in the entire population. These discrepancies were found in both sex and were unaffected by the HGS value at the start. In contrast to males, women had lower HGS values. The findings of the HGS (Handgrip Strength) were shown to have a negative association with age. Age, female gender, BMI, and dialysis modality were all linked to HGS findings on multiple regression. Following the dialysis both in males and females and in patients with normal and low baseline HGS outcomes, the conclusion of these articles indicates that HGS declines significantly. These articles have not been limited to investigate the effect on measurement of the day of the week. In addition, the reasons for HGS variances among patients were outside the scope of the study (inter-patient variability). The analysis of HGS variants among patients was also beyond the scope of the investigation (inter-patient variability). In this context, all potential aspects (inflammation, dialysis efficiency, etc.) that affect dialysis patients

have not been carefully examined. ⁽⁴⁾

A study "Assessment of the nutritional status of Nepalese hemodialysis patients by anthropometric examinations and modified quantitative subjective global assessment" by Arun Sedhain et.al using cross-sectional descriptive observational analysis by Modified Quantitative Subjective Global Assessment (MQSGA) with various Laboratory and Anthropometric measures such as mid-arm circumference, body mass index (BMI), biceps skinfold and triceps skinfold, mid-arm muscle circumference (MAC), serum albumin, C-reactive protein for nutritional status and result says according to MQSGA guidelines, 66.7% of the patients had slight to severe malnourished, while 33.3% were well maintained. None of the patients had serious malnutrition. CRP was shown to be positive in 56.3% of patients. MQSGA has a poor relationship with MAC. MQSGA was shown to have a negative association with total cholesterol, LDL (low-density lipoprotein) cholesterol, HDL (high-density lipoprotein), and triglycerides cholesterol, but there was no statistical significance. The conclusion of this article says mild to mild malnutrition was discovered in two-thirds of the hemodialysis patients. MQSGA was negatively associated with anthropometric measures such as mid-arm circumference, mid-arm muscle circumference, BMI, body surface area (BSA), and triceps skinfold. There were limitations in this article despite the fact that there were no very malnourished patients and the research engaged 96 percent of the population available at a hospital. The use of the Vernier caliper of the civil and mechanical engineers instead of the skinfold, which is not easily accessible on a local market, is also disadvantageous. ⁽⁶⁾

A study conducted by Kamyar Kalantar-Zadeh et.al namely "Design and Development of a Dialysis Food Frequency Questionnaire" included 893 patients receiving Hemodialysis at eight DaVita dialysis centers in the Los Angeles South Bay region with 154 in a sub-study of the GCRC on campus Harbor UCLA, where additional examinations were done including a three-day dietary survey. Study of the 154 hemodialysis patients' diet records revealed the significant contributors to their regular nutrient intake. A "Dialysis-FFQ" was created to incorporate about 100 food products that represented 90 percentage of the NIED Study population's total food consumption. Several meal items were differentiated according to essential nutritional difficulties in patients under dialysis, such as protein, potassium (K) and phosphorous (P), to score and compare dialysis patients based on their nutrition intake. The Dialysis-

FFQ (Food frequency questionnaire) may be a useful tool for comparing dialysis patients. Limitation of the study is Individual nutrient intake tends to be misunderstood; lack of precision in assessing the quantity or efficiency of individual or small communities of people's food consumption; inadequate coverage of a whole available dietary items; and the grouping of several types of a specific meal into a single food item, failing to record major distinctions between them.

A study conducted by Yoshiko Shutto. Et al. in Hirosaki City, Japan on "Inadequate Awareness among Chronic Kidney Disease Patients Regarding Food and Drinks Containing Artificially Added Phosphate". In this study including 153 patients (77 men and 76 females; average age 56 ± 11 years). List of questions was given to the participants which revealed that CKD patients on hemodialysis are unaware of the hidden amount of phosphate in their diet, emphasizing the necessity for learning activities to enhance CKD patient knowledge about this problem. limitation of study is due to a lack of knowledge of the phosphate amount, the majority of the questioned patients consumed soda and/or ate fast food, and so they did not get enough patients to construct a control group of non- consumers of these products. In urine samples obtained before and after consuming soda or water, abnormal excretion of urinary protein and sugar was not detected. This study did not look at the long-term consequences of soda intake on mineral ion metabolism. More research is needed to establish that elevated blood phosphate levels in patients who consume fast food and soda are not innocuous, and that an elevated phosphate diet is unjustifiable. ⁽³⁾

A study conducted by Caroline Finger Sostisso.et al. in the city of Curitiba, Brazil on "Handgrip strength as an instrument for assessing the risk of malnutrition and inflammation in hemodialysis patients." four HD clinics which included patients above 18 years age, have been on HD for at least three months, and have no neurocognitive restrictions in order to do the HGS test by author. 132 males (56%) were included in the trial, with ages ranging from 18 to 87 years (median = 59 years) and time on HD ranging from six months to 17 years (median = 25 months); 113 patients (47%) were over 60 years old. Results of this study shows the HGS cut-off value for detecting malnourishment and inflammatory processes was 14.5 kg for women and 23.5 kg for males. Malnourished patients were older (OR = 0.958), had lower arm circumference (OR = 1.328), had greater malnourishment and inflammation ratings (OR = 0.85), as per the HGS criteria. It concluded that nutritional evaluation indicators were substantially linked with HGS. These

findings imply that HGS is a reliable modality for hemodialysis patients who are at risk of malnutrition and inflammation. Limitations of this study. The lack of an accepted MIS reference standard is one of the study's weaknesses. In this study, the MIS value > 5 was utilized as the cutoff threshold; yet, other authors advocate other cutoff values depending on the population studied. The results offered by differences in age range - adults and the elderly - were not evaluated in this study; instead, we looked at differences between men and women. ⁽¹¹⁾

A study conducted by Viviane O.Leal M.S.et al. in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil on "Handgrip strength and its dialysis determinants in hemodialysis patients." Forty-three patients on HD (25 men, six diabetics, 54.5 ± 12.2 y of age, 62.2 ± 51.4 mo on dialysis) were included. Result of study shows HGS levels were substantially high in males before and after HD, but were not statistically varies in women (29.8 10.3 and 30.2 9.9 kg for men, 14.1 7.0 and 14.5 6.3 kg for women). A total of 24 patients (55.8%), 12 women and 12 men, had MF loss. Dialysis factors did not change among patients with and without MF loss, and there was no correlation between HGS assessed before and after an HD treatment. This study concluded that according to HGS, patients on HD had the excess rate of MF loss, which was unaffected by dialysis factors. HGS can be assessed before or after HD sessions to serve as a valid nutritional monitor. Limitation of study is lack of certain predicted correlations might be due to the small sample size, and the cross- sectional design prevents the evaluation of any causative relationships between dialysis factors and MF. ⁽¹²⁾

A study conducted by author Kazuhiko Tsuruya.et al. viz "Dietary Patterns and Clinical Outcomes in Hemodialysis Patients in Japan: A Cohort Study" from the Hisayama research (year 2007) included 3,080 participants and the Japan Dialysis Outcomes and Practice Patterns Study included 1,355 hemodialysis patients. result of this study shows Meat, fish, and vegetables were defined as three dietary categories. They next defined three eating patterns based on those groups: well-balanced, imbalanced, and other. They discovered a link between an imbalanced diet and major clinical outcomes after correcting for relevant variables. Author concluded that patients on hemodialysis who ate an imbalanced diet had a higher chance of having poor clinical results. Hemodialysis patients may profit not just from portion restriction, but also from a good-balanced diet that includes meat, fish, and vegetables. The fact that food consumption was self-reported is a drawback of this study. Due to social desirability skew, hemodialysis patients who

were aware of their dietary restrictions may have reported falsely low levels of food consumption, resulting in an inaccurate assessment of micronutrient consumption. ⁽⁹⁾

A study conducted by author Valeria M. Saglimbene et al. in European countries (France, Germany, Italy, Hungary, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden and Turkey) on “Dietary intake in adults on hemodialysis compared with guideline recommendations” included 6,906 adults undergoing hemodialysis in 10 European countries. Result shows Phosphate and potassium consumption in patients' diets were rarely in accordance with recommendations (consistent in 25 percent). Nearly half of the patients said their energy (45%) and calcium intake (53%) were within the guidelines, while 85 percent and 67 percent of patients said their sodium and protein intakes were within the guidelines, respectively. The results were identical in all of the nations that took part. Only 1% of patients had followed all six guideline criteria. Study concluded that patients on maintenance hemodialysis have a food habit that differs from current guidelines, particularly in terms of phosphate and potassium. Limitation of the study are dietary intake was dependent on a single assessment and was self-reported. The research depended on a food frequency questionnaire (FFQ), which was verified against plasma phospholipid fatty acids, but not with other nutritional assessment techniques or in the context of hemodialysis. Due to these restrictions, measurement errors and improper absolute dietary intakes may have occurred. ⁽¹⁰⁾

RESEARCH GAPS:

There is a limited data on dietary intake in chronic kidney disease patients. There are limited studies in Indian population on CKD patients' regular dietary pattern and finding of nutritional status in considering both diet and anthropometry.

NEED FOR STUDY:

There is a lack of data on dietary intake in chronic renal disease patients; most research did not evaluate what meals patients consumed alone and considering differences in Indian food culture. There have been very few studies in the Indian population on CKD patients' usual food patterns, as well as little data on Handgrip Strength (HSD) and Anthropometry.

Aim & Objectives

Aim:

To assess the diet pattern, anthropometry, and handgrip strength of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) patients undergoing hemodialysis (HD) in

tertiary care hospital.

Objectives:

- To assess the diet pattern in hemodialysis patient.
- To measure the nutritional anthropometry of hemodialysis patients.
- To determine the handgrip strength of patients on hemodialysis.

METHODOLOGY:

Study Design: Cross sectional study

Study Setting: Hemodialysis Unit
Department of Nephrology Grace Hospital and
Nursing Home, Kaliyakavilai

Participants: Patients on Hemodialysis

Sampling Method: Convenience sampling technique.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients on maintenance hemodialysis patients for more than three months with age above 18 years.

Exclusion criteria

- Patients on peritoneal dialysis treatment
- Patients who are in ICU
- Patients with AKI
- Patients with hand deformities

Sample Size: Time bound (100)

Procedure:

This is a cross sectional study on patients diagnosed with chronic kidney disease (CKD) who are on maintenance hemodialysis at Grace Hospital and nursing home, kaliyakavilai.

Patients are screened and selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria food frequency questionnaire was used to collect information diet intake of patients for three days. Handgrip strength was measured before and after dialysis using the Jamar dynamometer and skinfold thickness was measured for both biceps and triceps using vernier caliper.

OUTCOME MEASURES

- Dietary pattern.
- Handgrip strength.
- Anthropometry.

Data Analysis

- Statistical method: SPSS 16 version will be used for analysis and demographic characteristic will be analyzed using descriptive statistics.
- For descriptive purposes, the values were be presented as mean and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) for continuous variables and as weighted percentages for categorical variables.

RESULTS:

Totally 100 participants were recruited in this study those who were fulfilling the inclusion criteria

(n=100). Out of 100 participants, 79(79%) were men and 21(21%) were women, mean age was 50.75 ± 12.56 , mean height was 159.6 ± 10.86 , mean BMI is

22.22 ± 3.29 and dry weight was 56.68 ± 10.44 . Demographic details described in table-1.

TABLE 1

N=100	Age	Height	Weight	BMI
Mean	50.75 years	159.6cm	56.68kg	22.22kg/m ²
Standard deviation	12.56	10.86	10.44	3.29

The result shows the diet pattern of patients. Some of the foods consumed by patients in the morning are dosa, idly and puri, afternoon rice sambar and curd, in evening snack items like biscuits, bread, rusk and some fruits like apple, guava, pomegranate, watermelon, and orange, and then at night rice sambar and sometimes dosa or chapatti. Patients also take non-veg like chicken, fish, and egg. All these food items were identified while descriptively evaluating the diet.

Handgrip strength is measured both in left and right hands before and after dialysis using a Jamar hand dynamometer. The maximum and minimum value in

the left hand before dialysis is 48.23 and 11.7 and in the left hand after dialysis is 46.8 and 11.13. The maximum and minimum value in the right hand before dialysis is 49.23 and 14.23 and in the right hand after dialysis is 48.53 and 14.23. In the left hand, before and after dialysis we get a mean of 28.8 and 26.9 with standard deviations of 9.4 and 8.9 whereas in the right hand before and after dialysis, we get a mean of 32.0 and 30.4 with a standard deviation of 9.75 and 9.42 (table2). Table 3 shows the 95 percent confidence intervals for pair 1 is 1.57 and 2.31 and pair 2 is 1.21 and 1.87. There is significant reduction in handgrip strength after dialysis.

TABLE 2

		MEAN	N	STANDARD DEVIATION	STANDARD ERROR MEAN
PAIR 1	LEFT-HAND AVERAGE BEFORE	28.87800	100	9.4091619	.9409162
	LEFT-HAND AVERAGE AFTER	26.93300	100	8.9194884	.8919488
PAIR 2	RIGHT-HAND AVERAGE BEFORE	32.00130	100	9.751369	.9751369
	RIGHT-HAND AVERAGE AFTER	30.45600	100	9.4221363	.9422136

TABLE 3

	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	STANDARD ERROR MEAN	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL OF THE DIFFERENCE (LOWER)	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL OF THE DIFFERENCE (UPPER)	PAIRED TEST	DEGREE OF FREEDOM	SIGNIFICANT (2-TAILED)
PAIR 1	1.94500	1.8617864	0.1861786	1.522195	2.69805	10.064	99	.000
PAIR 2	1.5453	11.8717237	1.1871724	1.217132	1.873468	9.3434	99	.000

Pair 1 – an average of the left hand before and after Pair 2 – an average of the right hand before and after

In anthropometry, we measured the skin thickness of both biceps and triceps. we get the maximum and minimum value of biceps is 23.4mm and 8.7mm and in triceps maximum and minimum value is 23.5mm and 10.1mm with the mean of biceps and triceps is 14.3 and 15.24 and the standard deviation of biceps and triceps, 3.43 and 3.29 (Table 4). Average height, weight, and BMI are 159.6, 56.68, and 22.22. The result shows that triceps thickness linearly as when biceps thickness increases. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level and there is a positive correlation (table 5).

Table 4

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
BICEPS (mm)	100	8.7000mm	23.4000	14.305051	3.4306355
TRICEPS (mm)	100	10.1000	23.5000	15.241414	3.2957304

Table 5

		BICEPS (mm)	TRICEPS (mm)
BICEPS (mm)	Pearson Correlation	1	.947
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
TRICEPS (mm)	Pearson Correlation	.947	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	--
	N	100	100

DISCUSSION:

Our study included 100 participants. Dietary pattern observed was mostly vegetarian based example idly, dosa and their varieties, buri, pullav, vermicelli semiya, rice, chicken, fish, rasam, sambar, curd, buttermilk, some snacks items like biscuits, bread, rusk, some fruits like apple, guava, orange, grapes, pineapple and pomegranate, and raaji mal. When this descriptive data were compared to similar studies (2,3,10), two diet patterns emerged that are healthy and unhealthy, from both dialysis and non-dialysis patients, they calculated the phosphate and potassium intake through their daily diet and compared with recommended guidelines for dialysis patients. Diet pattern plays a vital role in assessing the nutrition intake but in this study, we get to know diet pattern

alone and assessment of nutrition element markers was not done. The diet pattern varied maybe because of the patient's financial status and geography. This study agrees that by evaluating patients' diet patterns, we can identify the nutritional level of that intake of sodium, potassium, phosphate, fluid, protein, etc. The number of patients enrolled in the study is adequate.

Measurement of the handgrip has been taken before and after hemodialysis on the same day. Handgrip strength is an easy, cheapest method for measuring muscle function and for assessing malnutrition. From the data analysis, we get to know that there is a decline

in the handgrip strength after the dialysis with a significant $p < 0.005$. This may be due to the dialysis process where in fluid is removed over the 4-hour period is not physiological, a dialysis treatment period is a major element of oxidant stress, that might be affecting muscle activity, and the dialysis stimulates more changes in different ions levels, which might affect muscle strength may be possible reasons for decline in strength after the treatment session. (4) When comparing this study with other studies (4,11,12), the same result that decline in handgrip strength after the dialysis was obtained. This handgrip strength can also be used in measuring malnutrition and muscle function because it predicts muscle endurance and overall strength. When the patient has a good nutritional intake their muscle growth will be good. In the current study, we did not measure muscle function and malnutrition. Hence handgrip strength can be used for both malnutrition and to determine muscle function. When compared to the previous study (12) the handgrip strength value not decreased after the dialysis this may be due to the sample size ($n=43$). In future studies handgrip strength measurement before and after can be done for three days or week to identify and overcome this opposite result with a large sample size.

In skin fold thickness we measured the thickness in their non-av fistula hand after the dialysis. Mostly we measured the skinfold thickness in the right because most of the patients have done left brachiocephalic av

fistula and for some patients, we measured in the left hand who had done av fistula in right brachiocephalic. As the data analysis shows that there is a positive correlation between both biceps and triceps that when biceps increase by 1 mm triceps will also increase 1mm. Normal biceps skinfold thickness is 15mm in males and 23mm in females, whereas the average triceps skinfold thickness in males is 12mm, and in females are, 23mm. Another study ⁽⁶⁾ correlates the BMI, biceps, and triceps with Modified Quantitative Subjective Global Assessment, where they get results as negative correlation, which is used for finding malnutrition. But in the current study, we correlated biceps with triceps to see whether there is a relation between these biceps and triceps. Biceps and triceps values are less in some dialysis patients; this may be due to malnutrition, inflammation, and lack of physical activity suggested for dialysis patients. Whenever an illness or accident makes moving an arm or legs hard or impossible, the loss of flexibility may lead to muscle wasting.

limitations of this study are that it was a single-center study so results maybe not be generalized and the diet is self-reported.

CONCLUSION:

The diet pattern of CKD patients undergoing hemodialysis is assessed. The handgrip strength of patients on hemodialysis is average. Nutritional Anthropometry suggest that biceps thickness is average and triceps is average and these are less than those in normal indicating malnutrition.

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